

Design and simulation of a coaxial slot antenna for heat therapy uses of cancerous tumors with the ability of penetration into the body

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Abstract

Liver cancer is one of the most dangerous types of cancer in the world. One of the treatments that have received a lot of attention in recent years is heat therapy and the use of electromagnetic waves to warm the tumor and weaken or eliminate it. The antennas presented so far to use in this treatment method either had an omnidirectional SAR distribution pattern or a directional SAR distribution pattern. In this research, we have designed and presented a coaxial slot antenna that has a semi-cylindrical slot with a reflector part to direct the radiation into one side. Also, there is a conical slot at the end of the structure that radiates omnidirectionally. Therefore, this antenna provides both types of radiation patterns simultaneously and in two separate frequencies. The operating frequency is 4.37 GHz for the omnidirectional radiation pattern and 9.26 GHz for the directional radiation pattern. The challenge that this structure creates is disabling one slot in the operating frequency of another slot. To surmount this issue, we use a low-pass step impedance filter between the slots to separate the operating area of the slots.

Keywords

Liver cancer; Hyperthermia; microwave ablation; coaxial slot antenna; heat therapy; omnidirectional radiation pattern; directional radiation pattern; step impedance filter

Introduction

Liver cancer is a common and deadly cancer in the world that occurs in the liver tissue. The disease begins when the body's cells in this tissue grow in an out of control manner. According to statistics published by the American Cancer Society in 2019, about 42030 cases of liver cancer (including 29480 men and 12550 women) have been reported, of which 31780 cases (including 21600 men and 10180 women) resulted in the death of the patient[1]. This statistic shows that it is important to pay attention to this disease and help treat it with the least side effects. Today, various methods such as virus therapy[2], radiation therapy[3], and chemotherapy are used to treat this type of cancer[4]. In recent years, with the development of techniques of radio frequency and microwave, the use of electromagnetic waves to treat diseases such as liver cancer and brain cancer has expanded[5]. Hyperthermia and microwave therapy are two important methods of using electromagnetic waves to treat cancer. In these methods, we direct electromagnetic waves to the location of the cancerous tumor by using different antennas to weaken or destroy the cancerous cells after radiation and increase the temperature of the tumor. The use of these methods, in addition to directly weakening or destroying the cancerous tumor, also increases the effectiveness of other therapies such as radiation therapy and chemotherapy on cancerous cells[6]. In the hypothermia method, the tumor temperature rises to about 42 to 45 C[7, 8], but in the microwave therapy method, the temperature of the target tumor rises to 60 C or more[9]. The designed antenna should have suitable and small dimensions so that they can easily enter the human body if needed and have fewer wound effects on the body. Also, the returned power from the antenna radiation place should be as low as possible to prevent the antenna from heating up and burning healthy tissues. Finally, the antenna radiation pattern must be uniformly distributed so that the heat reaches all parts of the cancerous tissue[10]. Therefore, antennas that have a rod or needle structure are more suitable for these applications. Among the antennas available in the telecommunication industry, monopole antennas, leaky wave antennas, and coaxial slot antennas are appropriate for this purpose. In the field of antenna design with the ability to penetrate into the body to treat cancer, the important point that arises after the small size of the antenna is to have a suitable pattern of the specific absorption rate (SAR)[11]. Many studies use a directional pattern of an antenna that enters the cancerous tumor center directly and radiates[12]. However, in many cases it is not possible to access the cancerous tumor center, or inserting an antenna into the cancerous tumor may be dangerous for the tumor itself or the surrounding healthy tissue. For example, in the liver cancer where the tumor is near the bowel or diaphragm, or in breast cancer where the tumor is attached to the chest, it is not possible to direct the antenna to the center of the cancerous tumor[13]. Therefore, in these situations, it is necessary to design an antenna that has a directional SAR pattern to be able to

Figure 1. The general structure of the proposed antenna

direct electromagnetic waves from one side to the target tumor. If we use a coaxial slot antenna, to achieve such a special absorption rate pattern, it is required to use appropriate reflectors at the antenna slots.

Proposed antenna structure

The antennas that have been designed and presented so far, depending on the application for which they were intended, either had an omnidirectional radiation pattern[14] or a directional radiation pattern[15]. To achieve these two types of patterns simultaneously and in two separate frequencies, it is necessary to separate the operating frequencies of these two slots. In this study, we designed a coaxial slot antenna that has a semi-cylindrical slot with a reflector part and a conical slot at the end of the structure. The semi-cylindrical slot operates at the frequency of 9.26 GHz and has a directional radiation. The conical slot operates at the frequency of 4.37 GHz and provide omnidirectional radiation pattern. By changing the operating frequency of the antenna, in this structure, any of these patterns can be accessed.

Figure 1, shows two views of the general structure of the antenna designed in the CST Studio software, which includes the slots on it. According to Figure 2, for a more detailed analysis of the different parts of the antenna, in addition to the longitudinal cutting along the antenna axis, we divide it into three parts A, B, and C, and analyze each one separately.

Figure 2. Different parts of the antenna

Part A, Impedance Matching Network

In order to better and more electromagnetic wave transmission from the desired gap to the liver tissue, we must match the characteristic impedance of the transmission line with the characteristic impedance of the liver tissue [16]. By changing the thickness of the external conductor and the thickness of the dielectric or changing the dielectric material, a suitable impedance matching can be achieved between the liver tissue and the characteristic impedance of the transmission line. The dielectrics used in this section are Rogers RO3006, Teflon, and air. Figure 3 and Table 1 show the details and sizes of the different parts.

Figure 3. Part A, Impedance Matching Network

Table 1. The values of the parameters of part A.

Parameter	Value (mm)	Parameter	Value (mm)
D1	0.5	D5	0.35
D2	0.3	L1	5
D3	0.75	L2	9
D4	0.7		

Part B, Directional slot

To have a directional radiation pattern, it is necessary to create a semi-cylindrical slot on the external conductor of the antenna. This slot has been shown to the left of Part B. In addition, to improve the directing of this slot to the antenna radiation pattern, a reflector with a length of 9 mm is embedded in its continuation, which is visible on the right side of part B. The details and size of the reflector and directional slot are shown in Figure 4 and Table 2.

Figure 4. Part B, Directional slot

Part C, Omnidirectional slot and step impedance low-pass filter

To achieve the radiation pattern in all directions, we created a conical slot at the end of the antenna to facilitate

Table 2. The values of the parameters of part B.

Parameter	Value (mm)
L3	0.5
L4	0.3
L5	0.75
L6	0.7

the injection of the antenna into the tissue in addition to achieving the desired pattern. In order to separate this radiation pattern from the directional pattern, we need to put a filter between these two slots so that when one of these slots is active, the other slot will not have radiation [17]. In this design, a step impedance low-pass filter is used. This filter passes waves with the operating frequency of the omnidirectional slot, which is 4.37 GHz, and at this frequency, only the omnidirectional slot radiates. As a result, the antenna generally has an omnidirectional radiation pattern. At the frequency of 9.26 GHz, which is the operating frequency of the directional slot, the filter does not transmit the waves and only the directional slot radiates. As a result, the antenna will generally have a directional radiation pattern. Figure 5 and Table 3 show more details and the size of the parameters in Part C.

Figure 5. Part C, the omnidirectional slot with the step impedance low-pass filter

Table 3. The values of the parameters of part C.

Parameter	Value (mm)	Parameter	Value (mm)
D6	1.2	L9	0.35
D7	1.8	L10	5
D8	1.6	L11	9
L7	1.2	L12	9
L8	1.6		

Results

An important point in designing this kind of antennas is to have the least amount of reflected power at the operating frequencies from the antenna. Because high returned power to the feed source may increase the temperature of the system and disrupt it.

The reflected power (S11) diagram in terms of frequency of the designed antenna is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Reflected power (S11) diagram in terms of frequency

Figure 7. SAR distribution pattern of the antenna at 4.37 GHz

As can be seen, in the operating frequencies of the antenna, which are the frequencies of 4.37 and 9.26 GHz, the amounts of reflected power are less than -10 dB, which are acceptable values.

To see how much electromagnetic energy is absorbed into the liver tissue at these frequencies, we use a measure called the specific absorption rate (SAR) [18, 19, 20]. Figure 7 shows the omnidirectional SAR distribution pattern of the antenna at 4.37 GHz through a conical slot, and Figure 8 shows the directional SAR distribution pattern of the antenna at 9.26 GHz through a semi-cylindrical slot. Figures 9 and 10 show the thermal distribution of the antenna at the frequencies of 4.37 GHz and 9.26 GHz after 10, 50, and 100 seconds, respectively.

Figure 8. SAR distribution pattern of the antenna at 9.26 GHz

To see how much electromagnetic energy is absorbed into the liver tissue at these frequencies, we use a measure called the specific absorption rate (SAR) [18, 19, 20]. Figure 7 shows the omnidirectional SAR distribution pattern of the antenna at 4.37 GHz through a conical slot, and Figure 8 shows the directional SAR distribution pattern of the antenna at 9.26 GHz through a semi-cylindrical slot. Figures 9 and 10 show the thermal distribution of the antenna at the frequencies of 4.37 GHz and 9.26 GHz after 10, 50, and 100 seconds, respectively.

Figure 9. Thermal distribution at the frequencies of 4.37 GHz

Figure 10. Thermal distribution at the frequencies of 9.26 GHz

Discussion

As explained in the previous sections, the use of antennae with a single radiation pattern is not applicable to many cancer cells. Therefore, it is necessary to use another antenna to be able to provide the desired radiation pattern. This requires money, time, and energy, and in addition, may cause the antenna to penetrate the tissue more than once, and over-injection of the antenna itself will damage the tissue. Hence, designing an antenna that has both types of radiation patterns in its structure and provides each of these radiation patterns by penetrating into the body once and changing the operating frequency of the antenna, will be a valuable advantage. The coaxial antenna designed in this article, using two different types of slots in its structure, provides two types of radiation patterns, each of which can be achieved by changing the

operating frequency of the antenna.

Conclusions

To achieve a structure with two types of radiation patterns, it is necessary to use both types of slots that were previously used independently and in separate structures. The challenge is how to separate the functional area of each of these slots. In this proposed scheme, we have seen that step impedance filters can solve this problem and allow us to have two types of SAR distribution patterns in one structure. Despite all the advantages listed above, the very small dimensions, along with the cylindrical structure of the antenna pose a serious challenge to build such a structure. However, we will try to confirm the results obtained in the near future by taking into account more preparations and building this type of antenna.

Author contributions

B.M. proposed the idea of designing this antenna structure and the relevant simulations were done by him. Challenges in the design path have been overcome with the guidance of Dr. K.F. and have led to the final design.

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